

Original Research Report

Repositioning Home Economics for Functional Entrepreneurship Education Programme in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria

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Abstract: This study aimed to discover the need for and approaches to repositioning Home Economics for a functional entrepreneurship education programme in Colleges of Education in the North-Central Zone of Nigeria. Four (4) specific objectives and Four (4) research questions guided the study. A descriptive survey design was used for the study. The population for the study comprised 73 Home Economics lecturers and 178 NCE III Students in Colleges of Education in North-Central, Nigeria. Sampling techniques were not carried out, all the populations were chosen for sample size because the population is small, manageable, and individual views were considered important for the study. A 48-item questionnaire developed by researchers and validated by experts was employed as an instrument for data collection. The reliability coefficient of the instrument is 0.745 using Cronbach Alpha. The researchers along with the research assistants administered the instrument to the respondents. Seventy-three (73) Lecturers' questionnaires were administered, seventy-three (73) were returned and one hundred and seventy-eight (178) student questionnaires were administered but one hundred and sixty-two (162) were returned successfully thereby giving 100% and 91% return rate. Mean was used to analyze the data. The study's findings revealed the need to reposition the Home Economics curriculum for functional Entrepreneurship Education in Colleges of Education in the North-Central Zone, Nigeria (Average Mean 3.44). Based on the findings, recommendations were made to include that Colleges of Education should adopt innovative curriculum design, teaching methods, assessment tools, and robust feedback mechanisms.

Keywords: Education, Entrepreneurship, Functional, Home Economics, Repositioning.

1. Introduction

Fundamentally, the Home Economics programme (HEP) has a lot of career opportunities for functional entrepreneurship education. These career opportunities in HEP include food processing and culinary arts, nursery school and daycare center management, fashion design, garment making or tailoring, fashion merchandising, fabric design, interior design, and decoration. household craft, event management, and venue decoration. All these careers are embedded in food and nutrition, home management, clothing and textile, consumer education, family and child development, personal and community health, hospitality industry and tourism education, and entrepreneurship (NCE Minimum Standard, 2020). According to the NCE Minimum standard implementation framework, each student must offer all these core courses which gives no room for a particular skill to be acquired. Thus, making students jack of all trades and master of none. To address these HEP needs to reposition to embedded specialization and generalization courses. The specialization courses would provide technical skills and knowledge on a particular career or enterprise. While generalization courses would provide broader knowledge of entrepreneurship education generally. Galvão, Marques, and Ferreira (2020) study revealed that learners participating in entrepreneurship education and training programmes positively impact the individual entrepreneurial orientation and skills, leading to the creation of new businesses and the strengthening of competencies.

Functional entrepreneurship education enhances students' career prospects and contributes to the economic development of the nation. There is global support for functional entrepreneurship education which has never been in doubt. Many scholars believe that entrepreneurship education remains the precursor to acquiring economic and industrial breakthroughs of a nation (Mu'azu, Abbas & Gidado 2018; Ereh, Anthony & Ikpo, 2019). Entrepreneurship education improves the ability to establish a business in the present and in entrepreneurial activities in the future (Lv *et.al.*, 2021). Entrepreneurship in Home Economics curriculum encourages the acquisition of entrepreneurship skills among students. However, many factors are affecting the quality implementation of the curriculum especially in Colleges of Education. Among these factors are curriculum issues itself, that is temporal and physical factors that hinder HEP from producing qualified and professional entrepreneurial educators to teach at the pre-basic, basic, and post-basic levels. Also, to produce graduates with potential entrepreneurial skills, knowledge, and positive attitudes needed for self-employment and wealth creation. Based on these challenges, repositioning HEP for functional entrepreneurship education for job, wealth creation, economic, and technological development of the nation become necessary.

1.1. Statement of Problem

The researchers observed that the learners engaged in different skill activities within limited instructional time which is inappropriate for teaching and learning entrepreneurship in Home Economics education. Also, entrepreneurship in the Home Economics curriculum course contents is overloaded, instructional strategies and the nature of assignments given to students cannot provide sound basic entrepreneurial knowledge and skills that learners need to establish and sustain a business

or production enterprise. Another issue of concern is that the quality and quantity of Home Economics graduates to meet the demand for Home Economics entrepreneurship teachers at the basic and post-basic levels of education are inadequate. There is a strong need for teachers in the areas of trade subjects such as garment making, the art of catering services, tie and die, textile trade, and cosmetology. This assertion is buttressed by Rotimi, Enimola, and Ochidi (2021) who observed that unemployment has always been a pitiful problem in African countries particularly in Nigeria, causing not only economic disruption but also a barrier to the fulfillment of dreams.

However, despite government efforts to fund entrepreneurship education in our tertiary institutions, some factors are not taken into consideration in terms of quality research in entrepreneurship education curricula. Shehu (2018) opined that vocational education programme needs entrepreneurship education with a curriculum specialization programme that will encourage full training and preparation of student teachers for professional entrepreneurship educators and economic entrepreneurs. Also, the researchers observed that studies carried out on Home Economics entrepreneurship education in Colleges of Education are few. This has created a gap, which this study on repositioning Home Economics for functional Entrepreneurship Education in Colleges of Education intends to fill. It is on this note that the study seeks to appraise repositioning Home Economics for functional Entrepreneurship Education in Colleges of Education.

1.2. Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of this research is to appraise the needs and approaches to repositioning Home Economics for functional Entrepreneurship Education in Colleges of Education in the North-Central Zone, Nigeria. The specific purpose is to:

- (a) examine the need to reposition Home Economics for functional Entrepreneurship Education in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria.
- (b) establish approaches to reposition Home Economics for functional Entrepreneurship Education in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria.
- (c) establish specialized Curriculum Modules for functional Entrepreneurship in Home Economics in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria.
- (d) ascertain generalized curriculum modules for functional Entrepreneurship in Home Economics in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria

1.3. Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- (a) What are the needs to reposition Home Economics for functional Entrepreneurship Education in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria?
- (b) What are the approaches to repositioning Home Economics for functional Entrepreneurship Education in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria?
- (c) What are the specialized curriculum modules for functional Entrepreneurship in Home Economics

in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria?

(d) What are the generalized curriculum modules for functional Entrepreneurship in Home Economics in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria?

1.4. Theory of Entrepreneurship Education

The theory of Entrepreneurship Education was propounded by Alberti, Sciascia, and Poli in 2004. The theory states that for effective entrepreneurship education, there should be a relationship between the goals of the entrepreneurship programme, the students to which the programme is delivered, the contents of the entrepreneurship course or modules, the method of delivery, and finally, the assessment that will be used. Alberti, et.al. maintained that entrepreneurship is a practice behaviour. It is a discipline and like any other discipline, it can be learned. The theory explains the relationship between entrepreneurship education, employable skills, and self-employment. This theory emphasizes that instead of seeking white-collar jobs, graduates of Nigerian Tertiary Institutions, given the rightful entrepreneurship education, should be job creators and innovators, not job seekers. With entrepreneurial studies entrenched in various curriculum contents, the expectation is that the unemployment rate among youths would drop.

1.4.1 Concept of Home Economics and Functional Entrepreneurship Education

Home Economics Education as a practical skill course with global importance has many areas of specialization and each area is grounded with a lot of entrepreneurial skills that can be acquired by students before and after graduation (Bob-Eze, 2023). However, Azonuche (2020) stressed that Home Economics as a subject impact both practical and theoretical knowledge in art and science with the use of the right technology in education. However inadequate time allocation for practical classes, lack of enough practical demonstrations, and obsolete equipment and tools` were factors that impede Home Economics for skill acquisition in tertiary institutions for economic empowerment. Fabusuyi (2012) recommended that there is a need for an entrepreneurial programme that will achieve self-employment and productivity; Home Economics Education should be given appropriate status at all levels of the education system to empower individuals and prepare them to become employers of labour and/or employees in the private or public sector of the economy; that schools should allocate enough time to practical teaching in the school timetable. Molokwu (2010) cited in Achor (2014) opined that re-branding can help Home Economics to stand out and achieve professional goals by renewing what is taught, what methods are used to teach to ensure what is taught is transferable and has value for the new times.

Home Economics teacher education needs functional entrepreneurship education to close gaps between the classroom and the real business world. Deryabina, Mozzhukhin, Pamukhin, and Potapova (2022) explained that teaching entrepreneurial competencies can enhance students' chances of securing jobs in small and medium-sized businesses. learners need functional Entrepreneurship Education that would enable them to use the knowledge and skills acquired for the creation of business and self-reliance. Ereh, et.al. (2019) explained that in ensuring proper

inculcation of entrepreneurial skills such as creativity, problem-solving, time management, communication, and leadership skills in graduates to gain knowledge, be able to understand the way the economy and market forces work, the educational system therefore needs to strengthen entrepreneurship education with a rich and appropriate curriculum course content. Also, Achor (2014) recommended that internet services should be made available and accessible to students to enable them access to current information on entrepreneurship. Su-ji (2007) points out that modular courses in college enterprise education enhance mutual integration, program operation, and entrepreneurship education results. It is therefore imperative that entrepreneurship curriculum content must be rich with practical experiences, relevant to the needs of the learners and society. It is only then the students' interest can be enlisted for effective learning to be equipped with useful skills that will lead to either gainful employment or self-employment as entrepreneurs (Ereh, et.al. 2019). Thus, it is believed that when the curriculum content is not relevant to the needs of the individuals, students, and society, students' interests will not be registered to enable effective learning, therefore the system is bound to produce poorly skilled graduates who cannot defend their certificates, thereby unable to secure or employment. This could mean that education has not gone beyond literacy and numeracy, and so, it is not functional (Bob-Eze, 2023).

Entrepreneurship education and skill acquisition in Home Economics can promote youth empowerment in Nigeria by providing essential skills for gainful employment or self-employment (Abanobi, 2017). Hence, there is a need for the repositioning of Home Economic Education for functional Entrepreneurship Education in Colleges of Education.

Functional Entrepreneurship Education with innovative assessment tools that evaluate students' entrepreneurial competencies and ability in business contexts, adequate temporal and physical factors to teach and learn quality Entrepreneurship Education, specialized training programs, and Project-Based Learning strategies. Li (2019) strengthens that the curriculum should be redesigned with innovative contents, methods, and fusion between specialties based on the clarification of the objectives of the curriculum and the development of specialty characteristics, thereby actively designing and constructing an entrepreneurial education curriculum system suitable for the training of financial and economic talents. The students can focus on specific fields such as fashion design, catering, interior design, or nutrition consultancy. This allows learners to acquire deep technical knowledge and practical skills in one area, increasing their marketability and job readiness in niche industries. Graduates can become experts in their fields, making them more competitive and capable of launching specialized businesses.

1.4.2 Review of Related Empirical studies

The study of Oluwade, Suleiman, and Olumoyegun (2022) on the effect of entrepreneurship education on self-employment initiatives at Federal University, Lokoja revealed that entrepreneurship curriculum with learners centered approaches and problem-solving approaches has a significant effect on self-employment initiatives of youth. In a related study, Ahmed (2018) correlation between Home

Economics education and entrepreneurial skills acquisition for wealth creation and poverty reduction in Nigeria revealed that a positive relationship exists between Home Economics education and innovation, creativity, and foresight skills. Similarly, Vaičekuskaitė and Valackienė (2018) study confirms a significant need for entrepreneurial education to start, develop, and successfully realize innovative ideas. More so, Aladejebi (2018) reported that entrepreneurship education positively influences the entrepreneurial intentions of Nigerian tertiary institution students, as many of them show the intention of starting their own business when they graduate based on data collected from 381 students from a university, polytechnic, college of education, and a satellite campus of a university. Correspondingly, Sun, Liang, and Wong (2017) study revealed that specific components of entrepreneurship education influence the attitudes and intentions of students, filling a knowledge gap needed to foster entrepreneurial intention through education. To bring out the entrepreneurial competencies in learners there is a need for a specialization curriculum and innovative learning approaches. Engraining entrepreneurial skills and practical activities to Home Economics students in the College of Education would provide the needed solution to the complex issues of poverty and unemployment among graduates and this call for functional entrepreneurship education. Also, providing specialization options in Home Economics alongside entrepreneurship skills, knowledge, and attitude would support students with indebt acquisition of entrepreneurship education. It is on this premises that the research on repositioning Home Economics for functional entrepreneurship education in North-central Nigeria was undertaken.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design for the Study

This study adopted a descriptive survey design.

2.1.1. Ethics Statement

A letter of request to respond to the questionnaire was attached to the questionnaire which requested for candid responses to the questionnaire and confidentiality of the information to be used for the purpose of this research only.

2.2. Area of the Study

The study area is Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria.

2.3. Population and Sample

The population for the study comprised seventy-three (73) Home Economics lecturers and one hundred and seventy-eight (178) 300-level Home Economics students obtained from the year 2024 departmental staff list of eleven (11) Colleges of Education in North-Central, Nigeria. The sample size comprised seventy-three (73) Home Economics Lecturers and one hundred and seventy-eight (178) Home Economics Students. No sampling techniques were carried out as all members of the population for the study were chosen because they were small, manageable, and individual views were considered important for the study.

2.4. Instrument for Data Collection

The researchers used a research-developed questionnaire titled: Repositioning Home Economics for Functional Entrepreneurship Education Programme Questionnaire (RHEFEDPQ) which contained 47 items arranged in four clusters. Sections A, B, C, and D sought information on the specific objective of the study. Responses to the items were based on a four Likert scale ranging from Strongly Agree (4), to Agree (3), Disagree (2), and Strongly Disagree (1). The instrument was validated by two experts from the Department of Home Economics. A pilot testing was conducted in the College of Education, FCT, Zuba, and Kaduna State Colleges of Education, Gidan Waya. A total of sixteen (18) Home Economics Lecturers and twenty-three (23) students were involved for the pilot testing. A reliability coefficient of 0.745 was established using Cronbach Alpha. The alpha score for the questionnaire was considered high enough for the purpose of this study. Evidence that the RHEFEDPQ is highly reliable. This is in agreement with the confirmation test of reliability by Bashir and Marudhar (2018). According to them, an instrument is considered reliable if it lies between 0 and 1, and the higher the calculated reliability coefficient is to 1, the high reliable is the instrument, and the closer the calculated reliability coefficient is to 0, the less reliable is the instrument.

2.5. Data Collection Technique

The researchers with the help of three research assistants visited the Colleges of Education, introduced themselves to HODs requested permission to administer the questionnaire. With permission of HODs, the Researchers administered the questionnaire to the respondents and retrieved it after completion. There was difficulty in retrieving the entire questionnaire at once but the opportunity was given to respondents to send it to the Researchers through the post. Seventy-three (73) Lecturers questionnaires were administered, seventy-three (73) filled instruments returned and one hundred and seventy-eight (178) Students questionnaire were administered but one hundred and sixty-two (162) were returned successfully thereby giving 100% and 91% returned.

2.6. Data Analysis Technique

The Researchers cross-examined the questionnaires to ascertain the returned rate and completeness. The data obtained from the respondents was analyzed using the mean formula. A criterion mean of 2.50 was set for the study. The limit for decision rule: An average mean of 2.50 and above was considered as agreed, while an average mean below 2.50 was considered as disagreed. Mann-Whitney (U Test) was used to test the null hypotheses All the null hypotheses were tested for rejection or acceptance at 0.05 alpha level of significance. The limit for a decision on hypotheses: if $U_{obt} \leq U_{crit}$, $U_{obt} \geq U_{crit}$ at 0.05 level of significance then the results are significant, and the null hypotheses will be rejected. If otherwise the alternative hypothesis is affirmed.

3. Results and Discussion

Table 1: Mean Score of Respondents on the Needs to Reposition Home Economics for Functional Entrepreneurship Education in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria.

S/No	Items	Respondents			Decision
		Lecturers Mean	Students Mean	Average Mean	
1	A need for sufficient semester course for functional Entrepreneurship Education in Home Economics Education	3.41	3.60	3.51	Agreed
2	Specialized courses in Entrepreneurship Education in Home Economics is required	3.33	3.57	3.45	Agreed
3	A need for adequate entrepreneurship curriculum in Home Economics for functional Entrepreneurship Education.	3.36	3.58	3.47	Agreed
4	Entrepreneurship in Home Economics Education needs Innovative teaching methods.	3.34	3.62	3.48	Agreed
5	Functional Entrepreneurship Education needs assessment tools that evaluate students' entrepreneurial competencies and ability in business contexts	3.19	3.48	3.34	Agreed
6	Adequate temporal factors to teach and learn quality Entrepreneurship Education is needed	3.04	3.60	3.32	Agreed
7	Adequate physical factors to teach and learn quality Entrepreneurship Education is needed	3.38	3.61	3.50	Agreed
8	A need for career awareness in Home Economics Entrepreneurship Education specialization	3.41	3.58	3.50	Agreed
Aggregate Mean				3.45	Agreed

Source: Field Survey 2024.

Table 1 revealed that the 8 items for lecturers' and students' responses had an aggregate mean of 3.45 which was above the benchmark of 2.50. This indicates that the respondents agreed that there is a need to reposition Home Economics for functional Entrepreneurship Education in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria. This is in line the finding Bob-Eze (2023) study on repositioning Home Economics education in Tertiary Institutions through clothing and textiles entrepreneurial skills for economic empowerment. The study found that inadequate time allocation for practical classes, lack of enough practical demonstrations, and obsolete equipment and tools' were factors that impede Home Economics for skill acquisition in tertiary institutions for economic empowerment. To boost functional Entrepreneurship Education in Home Economics, there is a need for sufficient semester courses, specialized and generalized courses, innovative teaching methods,

assessment, adequate temporal and physical factors, and career awareness must receive the necessary attention.

Table 2: Mean Score of Respondents on the Approaches Repositioning Home Economics for Functional Entrepreneurship Education in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria.

S/No	Items	Respondents		Average Mean	Decision
		Lecturers Mean	Students Mean		
1	Entrepreneurship in Home Economics Education should be redesigned to fit into areas of specialization courses.	3.38	2.90	3.14	Agreed
2	Entrepreneurship in Home Economics Education should be redesigned to fit into generalized courses.	3.20	3.11	3.16	Agreed
3	Entrepreneurship in Home Economics Education should be redesigned to fit both specialization and generalization courses.	3.50	3.33	3.42	Agreed
4	Instructional delivery time for specialization courses should take three to four hours	3.36	3.26	3.31	Agreed
5	Emphasis should be on use of Innovative Teaching Methods.	3.46	3.18	3.32	Agreed
6	Assessment tools to measure students' entrepreneurial competencies, such as creativity, risk-taking, business acumen, and problem-solving skills should be developed.	3.54	3.16	3.35	Agreed
7	Robust feedback mechanisms to continuously improve the curriculum and teaching methods based on student and industry feedback should be implemented.	3.45	3.43	3.44	Agreed
8	Government and institutions should enhance infrastructure for quality teaching and learning.	3.66	3.52	3.59	Agreed
9	Government and institutions should boost instructional resources for quality teaching and learning.	3.60	3.48	3.54	Agreed
10	Home Economics Professional bodies should advocate for support from government and institutional policies that prioritize entrepreneurship education within Home Economics programs.	3.54	3.40	3.47	Agreed
Aggregate Mean				3.38	Agreed

Source: Field Survey 2024.

Table 2 shows that the 10 items for lecturers' and students' responses had an aggregate mean of 3.38 which was above the benchmark of 2.50. This indicates that the respondents agreed that the 10 items are approaches to repositioning Home Economics for functional Entrepreneurship Education in

Colleges of Education in North-Central, Nigeria. This finding also agrees with Molokwu (2010) cited in Achor (2014) which found that re-branding can help Home Economics stand out and achieve professional goals by renewing what is taught, what methods are used to teach to ensure what is taught is transferable and has value for the new times. Equally, Abanobi (2017) established that entrepreneurship education and skill acquisition in Home Economics can promote youth empowerment in Nigeria by providing essential skills for gainful employment or self-employment. It is very necessary to apply these approaches in repositioning Home Economics for functional Entrepreneurship Education. Implementation of this innovative approach of redesigning the Home Economics curriculum for specialization and generalization in entrepreneurship education can lead to skilled, versatile graduates who are better prepared to thrive in competitive markets and create businesses. However, it also demands careful planning and support to ensure students receive a well-rounded education and skills for the development of business enterprise, teachers are adequately trained, and resources are adequately available. Maintaining a balance between broad skills and in-depth knowledge is key to achieving long-term economic and educational success.

Table 3: Mean Score of Respondents on the Relevance Specialization Curriculum Modules for Functional Entrepreneurship in Home Economics Education in Colleges of Education North-Central, Nigeria.

S/No	Items	Respondents			Decision
		Lectures Mean	Students Mean	Average Mean	
1	Food processing and Culinary Arts	3.60	3.47	3.54	Agreed
2	Nursery School and Daycare Centre Management	3.46	3.15	3.31	Agreed
3	Fashion Design	3.57	3.38	3.48	Agreed
4	Garment Making/ Tailoring	3.61	3.44	3.53	Agreed
5	Fashion merchandising	3.45	3.12	3.29	Agreed
6	Fabric Design	3.62	3.40	3.51	Agreed
7	Interior Design and Decoration	3.59	3.50	3.55	Agreed
8	Household Craft	3.56	3.32	3.44	Agreed
9	Event Management and Venue decoration	3.61	3.48	3.55	Agreed
Aggregate Mean				3.12	Agreed

Source: Field Survey 2024

Table 3 reveals that the 9 items for Lecturers' and Students' responses had an average mean of 3.12 which was above the benchmark of 2.50. This implied that the respondents agreed with all 9 items as the relevant curriculum modules for specialization courses and functional Entrepreneurship in Home Economics Education in Colleges of Education North-Central, Nigeria. This finding is in support of Li (2019) who recommended that the curriculum should be redesigned with innovative contents, methods, and fusion between specialties based on the clarification of the objectives of the curriculum

and the development of specialty characteristics, thereby actively designing and constructing an entrepreneurial education curriculum system suitable for the training of financial and economic talents. Students can focus on specific fields such as fashion design, catering, interior design, or nutrition consultancy. This allows learners to acquire deep technical knowledge and practical skills in one area, increasing their marketability and job readiness in niche industries. Graduates can become experts in their fields, making them more competitive and capable of launching specialized businesses.

Table 4: Mean Score of Respondents on the Relevance Generalization Curriculum Modules for Functional Entrepreneurship in Home Economics in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria.

S/No	Items	Respondents			Decision
		Lectures Mean	Students Mean	Average Mean	
1	Introduction to Entrepreneurship Education	3.59	3.34	3.465	Agreed
2	Collaboration and innovation of new products	3.41	3.08	3.245	Agreed
3	Business Mathematics	3.30	3.01	3.155	Agreed
4	Entrepreneurship Ethics and social responsibility	3.50	3.07	3.285	Agreed
5	Principle of Bookkeeping	3.38	3.04	3.21	Agreed
6	Business Planning and Management	3.36	3.25	3.305	Agreed
7	Marketing and Sales Education	3.51	3.03	3.27	Agreed
8	Personal, economics and social education	3.36	2.90	3.13	Agreed
9	Legal and regulatory issues	3.31	3.00	3.155	Agreed
10	Managing information Technology and E- trade in Home Economics Entrepreneurship	3.49	3.14	3.315	Agreed
11	Portfolio development and Investment issues	3.35	2.77	3.06	Agreed
12	Sustainability and Environmental Stewardship	3.43	3.03	3.23	Agreed
13	. Communication and Interpersonal Skills	3.52	3.10	3.31	Agreed
14	Leadership and Personal Development	3.46	3.21	3.335	Agreed
15	Research methods in Entrepreneurship Education	3.49	3.04	3.265	Agreed
16	Innovative teaching methods of Entrepreneurship Education	3.49	3.27	3.38	Agreed
17	Business proposals, presentations and fund sourcing	3.36	3.23	3.295	Agreed
18	Consumer needs, behavior and protection	3.63	3.40	3.515	Agreed
19	Students' industrial works experience (SIWES) / Internship	3.28	3.45	3.365	Agreed
20	Entrepreneurship Education Practicum	3.59	3.33	3.46	Agreed
Aggregate Mean				3.29	Agreed

Source: Field Survey 2024

Table 4 revealed that the 20 items for Lecturers' and Students' responses had an aggregate mean of 3.29 which was above the benchmark of 2.50. This indicated that the respondents agreed with all

20 items as the relevant curriculum modules for generalization courses for functional Entrepreneurship in Home Economics in Colleges of Education in North-Central Zone, Nigeria. This supported the findings of Deryabina, et.al. (2022) that teaching entrepreneurial competencies in non-core areas of undergraduate programs can enhance students' chances of securing jobs in small and medium-sized businesses. Equally, Su-ji (2007) opined that modular courses in college enterprise education enhance mutual integration, program operation, and entrepreneurship education results. A broad curriculum ensures students develop a diverse set of competencies which include financial literacy, customer service, and problem-solving that are applicable across various sectors. This approach promotes multidisciplinary thinking and encourages students to adapt to multiple career paths in business management and leadership, marketing sales, information technology, and E-trade.

Implications

The study established that functional entrepreneurship in Home Economics needs to be repositioned by redesigning a ground-breaking curriculum with sufficient semesters on specialization and generalization courses, innovative teaching methods, assessment, adequate temporal, and physical factors. When the findings and recommendations established by the study are published and implemented, it will be beneficial to NCE Students in acquiring functional entrepreneurship education. Also, cultivating students' entrepreneurial skills to prepare them for the demands of the modern economic and small-scale enterprise. Equally, engraining of entrepreneurial skills and practical activities in Home Economics to Students in College of Education will provide the needed solution to the complex issues of poverty and unemployment among NCE Students and NCE graduates.

Limitations

It should be noted that this study was conducted in only one Zone of the country. The restriction is useful for controlling variability, but caution is necessary for the generalization of the study. Also, the study faces challenges in getting access to all respondents due to the reduction of staff because of retirement and death.

Suggestions for further research

A similar study should be carried out in another zone of the country.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that there is a need to reposition Home Economics for functional Entrepreneurship Education. Correspondingly, approaches established by the study to reposition Home Economics for functional Entrepreneurship Education would diminish the adage of jack of all trades and master of all. Also, it would redeem the image of the Home Economics programme. Also, relevant specialized and generalized modules established by the study would support quality and functional entrepreneurship education as well as the production of NCE students' expertise in different specialized areas in Home Economics. These will boost the acquisition of innovative entrepreneurial skills among students.

Recommendations

In line with the findings of this study, the following recommendations are hereby proffered:

- i. Colleges of Education should adopt innovative curriculum design, teaching methods, assessment tools and robust feedback mechanism. These strategies will help the students in acquiring functional entrepreneurship education. Also, cultivating students' entrepreneurial skills to prepare them for the demands of the modern economic landscape.
- ii. Home Economics Professional bodies should advocate for support from relevance government agency to establish policies that prioritize entrepreneurship education within Home Economics programme.
- iii. National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) should engage experts in Home Economics curriculum development in designing Curriculum that embrace specialization and generalization courses for functional Entrepreneurship in Home Economics in Colleges of Education.
- iv. Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) should give more opportunities to Home Economics Programme in Colleges of Education in the areas of providing adequate physical infrastructure, ICT gargets and industrial equipment to facilitate Practical skills acquisition and functional Entrepreneurship Education. In addition, National Research Grand should be given to Home Economics Lecturers to carry out comprehensive research across six geo-political zones in Nigeria on innovative specialized and generalized curriculum design for functional Entrepreneurship.
- v. Home Economics Professional bodies should collaborate with National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE), Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) and small-scale industry for pilot testing the implementation of proposed curriculum after comprehensive research on innovative specialized and generalized curriculum design for functional Entrepreneurship education across six geo-political zones in Nigeria.

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Conflict of Interest

No conflict of interest affected the data collected and the findings of this study. The researchers try as much as possible to mitigate any conflict of interest in this study. The researchers maintain objectivity by adhering to ethical research standards. Engage external reviewers to ensure findings

are unbiased. Also, the researchers avoid undue influence from stakeholders by clarifying that research findings will be driven by data, not expectations.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization: IJS

Formal analysis: IJS and JA

Funding Acquisition: IJS, JA and MA

Investigation: IJS, JA and MA

Methodology: IJS, JA and MA

Data Analysis: IJS, JA and MA

Data Availability Statement

The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article: further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author

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